

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A data-driven global observatory addressing worldwide challenges through text mining and complex data visualisation [version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]

Joao Costa ^{1,2}, M. Beshar Massri^{1,3}, Marko Grobelnik¹⁻³, Ignacio Casals del Busto⁴, Dale Weston⁵

¹UNESCO International Research Institute on AI - IRCAI, Ljubljana, Slovenia

²Quintelligence, Ljubljana, Slovenia

³Institute Jozef Stefan, Ljubljana, Slovenia

⁴Aguas del Alicante, Alicante, Spain

⁵Public Health England, Salisbury, UK

V1 First published: 30 May 2022, 2:68
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14471.1>

Latest published: 07 Dec 2023, 2:68
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14471.2>

Abstract

Observing the world on a global scale can help us understand better the context of problems that engage us all. In this paper, we propose a data-driven global observatory that puts together the different perspectives of media, science, statistics and sensing over heterogeneous data sources and text mining algorithms. We also discuss the implementation of this global observatory in the context of epidemic intelligence, monitoring the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, and in the context of climate change, with a specific focus on water resource management. We will also discuss the value of this global solution in local contexts and priorities.

Keywords

Big Data, Semantic Technologies, Public Health, Water Management, Text Mining, MeSH Headings, MEDLINE, multilingual news, Social media

This article is included in the [Horizon 2020](#) gateway.

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

	1	2
version 2 (revision) 07 Dec 2023		 view
version 1 30 May 2022	 view	

1. **Haowen Xu**, Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Bethel Valley Road, USA

2. **Carson Leung** , University of Manitoba, Manitoba, Canada

Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

This article is included in the [Research on Research gateway](#).

This article is included in the [Data Science gateway](#).

Corresponding author: Joao Costa (joao.pitacosta@quintelligence.com)

Author roles: **Costa J:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Investigation, Methodology, Project Administration, Software, Supervision, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Massri MB:** Investigation, Resources, Software, Visualization, Writing – Review & Editing; **Grobelnik M:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – Review & Editing; **Casals del Busto I:** Validation, Writing – Review & Editing; **Weston D:** Validation, Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreements No 727721, A holistic water ecosystem for digitisation of urban water sector (NAIADES) and No 820985, Meaningful Integration of Data, Analytics and Services (MIDAS).

The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Copyright: © 2022 Costa J *et al.* This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

How to cite this article: Costa J, Massri MB, Grobelnik M *et al.* **A data-driven global observatory addressing worldwide challenges through text mining and complex data visualisation [version 1; peer review: 2 approved with reservations]** Open Research Europe 2022, 2:68 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14471.1>

First published: 30 May 2022, 2:68 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14471.1>

I. Plain language summary

In this research paper we lay the foundations for a data-driven perspective on how to appropriately use open data to build business intelligence, with proven usefulness in applications to public health and water resource management.

II. Introduction

The world’s globalization phenomena unveiled awareness of worldwide problems, such as the climate crisis, but also to common efforts to find solutions to those problems, as was the case of the several COVID-19 collaborative actions. There are many obstacles still today on such global strategies to which innovative technology and data-driven solutions can help. In this paper we propose the concept of a global observatory based on text mining algorithms that is able to answer the wide range questions that are core to global solutions, using Big Data analytic methods over the layered information it is ingesting in real-time. The main perspectives of this global observatory fall on: (i) the monitoring and exploration of news articles and social media feeds; (ii) the analysis of combinations of indicators through time and what stories can they tell; and (iii) the exploration of published scientific knowledge. All of these perspectives can be combined to provide complementary answers to main topics from health to engineering.

III. Methods

Taking into account the schema in Figure 1, we consider the construction of the Global Water Observatory into phases going from lower to higher complexity. We start by putting together data sources that are meaningful to a range of stakeholders that are targeted, from engaged citizens to decision makers that can leverage the information provided to established evidence-based policies.

At the data collection phase, we are concerned with addressing properly the challenges in the heterogeneous nature of the data, their different frequency and size, as well as the levels of access to it established by data providers. These parameters to take into consideration ensure the appropriate data ingestion into the system. The selection of data sources is done manually, but their ingestion is automated, and their frequency of update depends solely of the data provider. At this stage we are collecting data from many different data sources (such as, e.g., the Worldwide news, the Microsoft Academic Graph, the Word Bank, the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals), according to their relation to the focus topics and priorities.

A forthcoming stage is in the data cleaning, data processing and data integration prior ingestion. This step is highly important to allow for the data quality that is needed in order to obtain useful insights from it. In this step we include the data curation, where the most meaningful datasets are selected and parsed. We also include the exploratory data analysis and some data visualisation for the purpose of prototyping what is then available at the Water Observatory.

The Observatory phase is then possible when the curated data streams of a selection of dynamic data sources are live in the system and can be used to obtain insight on particular topics of interest, monitor Key Performance Indicators associated with business priorities, and allow for a global and local perspective on related topics. These include interactive data visualisations of indicators and statistical data, the dynamic view of the news sources over priorities, or the user query over a scientific research topic. This allows for insight on topics in analysis (such as water topics like, e.g., water scarcity and water quality, and public health topics like, e.g., ebola or the new coronavirus) that will be put into the context of local data when sourced from the shared interest of users.

The path ahead is a novel concept of a meaningful Digital Twin (i.e., a dynamical model which, given a current state of an observed system, is capable of a digital partial reconstruction of such a system) that builds over the Global Water Observatory to rise above data complexity towards data interoperability. This is usually difficult to achieve in full due to the heterogeneity of the data, the different characteristics of the data sourced (frequency, data types, etc.) and the domain knowledge needed to identify new challenges covering a wide range of business intelligence priorities. Nevertheless, useful aspects of it can be achieved, some of which are already evident from the implementations discussed in Section 6 and Section 7. An example of this is to track a topic in the news, its impact in the social media, and explore the range of the problem in the published scientific research, as well as extract good practices to deal with this problem.

We add a final stage to this diagram that is usually forgotten in a theoretical framework, which is the adaptation of the system to the needs and priorities in the user side. Here we consider the ingestion of local data, the customization of news streams, the availability of exploratory dashboards, the shareable instances for policy makers, and the APIs for 3rd party integration. A typical example of the aimed outcome of such an intelligent

Figure 1. The approach used leading from data sensing to the digital twin and its approximation to local priorities.

Figure 3. The IRCAI observatory for the COVID-19 pandemic.

Figure 4. The SDG6 observatory focused on water-related priorities.

Due to the rapidly growing awareness of the sustainability challenges that we are facing in Europe and worldwide in the context of the water resource management, there has been much work done to develop systems that are able to collect information about the available water and even simulate and forecast that in the near future. These are usually geolocation-based systems ingesting water-related data to enable real-time monitoring of resources and usage²³. The other typical approach is the systems focused on workflows in the water sector, including the management of water distribution networks, hydraulic efficiency or leak/fraud detection, better suited to those companies that already have their infrastructure in place and know well what do they want to monitor²⁴.

The approach we proposed in this paper is novel in many ways. The news monitoring perspective is monitoring water scarcity and water quality in worldwide and, in particular, in the surrounding regions of the water resource management agencies is mainly addressing, together with their audiences. This is also including a Twitter observatory that adds to the already implemented measure of impact of the monitored news in Facebook, a social media component to the observatory. The global indicators that are already available for visualisation, sourced over the UN Open Data Portal, the water-focused Sustainable Development Goal 6, and the World Bank Data Portal, can help us understand water-related aspects of the climate crisis.

The important role of scientific research in this context, and the best practices that can be extracted from this data, is explored with a complex data visualisation technology that allows the user to powerful Lucene-based queries over the article's metadata aiming to refine search by moving a pointer over clusters of related topics (see [Figure 5](#)). We will also be including other data analytics technologies to analyse simultaneously multiple time-series providing interactive exploration tools to understand trends in the weather and water-related impacts to it.

The localisation of this global system entails the customisation of its functionality in news monitoring, ingestion of local indicators and exploration of scientific research on observed problems in, *e.g.*, groundwater contamination. In that, the

observatory is synchronising with the priorities of regional water providers. These agencies (*e.g.* Aguas de Alicante) are collecting data on their water resource management services to improve the customer satisfaction and optimise their system.

VI. Conclusions and future work

The results discussed in this paper show the potential impact of the proposed data-driven global observatory in contexts like public health and climate change preparedness. This integrated system is capable to monitor in real-time the worldwide news and social media, statistics, published science, weather and many other data streams that are identified as useful and can be provide complementary value to those considered already. We will be deploying this system in the context of other global problems where there is enough data to provide useful and meaningful contribution, either in other aspects of the climate crisis to better plan response, in addressing other epidemiological concerns to serve as early warning, or in addressing a new focus in the context of data science for social good.

We are now working on extending this system to integrate the information retrieved by the topics searched over the internet provided by Google Trends, regarding issues related to the context in focus. The user will be able to explore a wide range of indicators and compare trends in a global and local level throughout a meaningful timeline. We will also be reusing EC-funded open datasets and initiatives in order to ingest this information as European-level indicators to complement the analysis. Furthermore, we will be further investigating the validity of the localization of this Global Water Observatory, integrating some of the local data that can be provided by the user, and customizing news sources to their own priorities, as well as making available data exploration dashboards that allow for further insight and evidence-based policy.

VII. Data availability

For this paper, we used only open data. In particular, we have used the MEDLINE dataset²⁵ and the worldwide news are being collected by [26](#), freely available online, but which the dataset we do not have permission to share.

VIII. Ethics and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required

References

1. World Health Organization: **WHO Director-General's opening remarks at the media briefing on COVID-19 -11 March 2020**. [Reference Source](#)
2. ArcGIS: **WHO COVID-19 Dashboard**. 2020. [Reference Source](#)
3. Kaggle: **COVID-19 Open Research Dataset Challenge**. [Reference Source](#)
4. medRxiv: **COVID-19 SARS-CoV-2 preprints from medRxiv and bioRxiv**. 2020. [Reference Source](#)
5. Zenodo **Coronavirus Disease Research Community**. 2020. [Reference Source](#)
6. IRCAI: **Coronavirus Watch portal**. 2020. [Reference Source](#)
7. **WorldoMeters**. 2020. [Reference Source](#)
9. Google: **COVID-19 Community Mobility Report**. 2020. [Reference Source](#)
8. **Center for Disease Control and Prevention**. 2020. [Reference Source](#)
10. Massri B, Costa JP, *et al.*: **A global COVID-19 observatory, monitoring the pandemics through text mining and visualization**. Informatica (manuscript in revision), Slovenian Society Informatika, 2021.

11. Pita Costa J, Grobelnik M, Fuart F, *et al.*: **Meaningful Big Data Integration For a Global COVID-19 Strategy**. *Computer Intelligence Magazine*. IEEE, 2020; **15**(4): 51–61.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
12. European Commission: **European Green Deal**. 2019.
[Reference Source](#)
13. European Commission: **Water Scarcity and Droughts in the European Union**. 2019.
[Reference Source](#)
14. **NAIADES Project Portal**. 2021.
[Reference Source](#)
15. **NAIADES Water Observatory**. 2020.
[Reference Source](#)
16. Our World in Data: **Water Use Stress**. 2020.
[Reference Source](#)
17. United Nations Development Programme: **Goal6 -clean water and sanitation**. 2020.
[Reference Source](#)
18. Blazhevskva V: **United Nations launches framework to speed up progress on water and sanitation goal**. United Nations Sustainable Development, 2020.
[Reference Source](#)
19. OECD: **Water governance in OECD countries: A multi-level approach**. OECD, 2011.
[Reference Source](#)
20. Akhmouch A, Clavreul D, Glas P: **Introducing the OECD principles on water governance**. *Water International*. 2018; **43**(1): 5–12.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
21. Freeze RA, Harlan RL: **Blueprint for a physically-based, digitally-simulated hydrologic response model**. *J Hydrol*. 1969; **9**(3): 237–258.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
22. Ramamoorthi A: **Snow-melt run-off studies using remote sensing data**. *Sadhana*. 1983; **6**(3): 279–286.
[Reference Source](#)
23. Idrica: **Blue Dot Observatory**. 2018.
[Reference Source](#)
24. Idrica: **GoAigua - Smart Water for a Better World**. 2019.
[Reference Source](#)
25. North American National Library of Medicine: **MEDLINE: Description of the Database**. 2022.
[Reference Source](#)
26. Institute Jozef Stefan: **IJS Newsfeed: a clean, continuous, real-time aggregated stream of semantically enriched news articles from RSS-enabled sites across the world**. 2022.
[Reference Source](#)

Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status: ? ?

Version 1

Reviewer Report 10 July 2023

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.15624.r32818>

© 2023 Leung C. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Carson Leung

University of Manitoba, Manitoba, Canada

Costa et al. described in this 8-page submission a data-driven global observatory addressing two worldwide challenges (namely, public health and water) through text mining and complex data visualisation. They focused on using open data appropriately to monitor news articles and social media feeds related to COVID-19 and water shortage. They would collect, clean, process, integrate and ingest data by making use of KPI and digital twin.

The presented idea is interesting. It would be nice if the authors could consider presenting the work more clearly and providing more details, especially for the corona virus watch observatory. For instance, the authors briefly described how to monitor news articles and social media feeds related to water shortage and quality. However, shorter descriptions were provided for COVID-19.

It would also be nice if the authors could consider providing more details of methods and analysis to allow replication by others. For instance, it is unclear what text mining techniques or what complex data visualisation was used.

Out of the list 26 references, only 5 were from journals. It would be nice if the authors could consider citing some more current formal literature.

It would be nice if the authors could consider further proofreading. For instance, the authors may want to replace the typo "nnd" by "and".

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Big data, public health, COVID-19, text mining, social media, data visualisation, data science

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 28 Nov 2023

Joao Costa

We again thank the useful review provided, leading us to improve the content of this paper both in regards to the citations to the related-work and to the details of the study. The time passed between the first submission and this new version also changes the relevance and novelty of the results described, but having in consideration that this is more of a position paper, the content remains useful now that it is better referenced.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 29 June 2023

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.15624.r32819>

© 2023 Xu H. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Haowen Xu

Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Bethel Valley Road, USA

Overall Comments:

This manuscript provides a comprehensive review of big data-driven methods for addressing

public health and water resources management problems using text mining and complex data visualization. The contributions of this manuscript include some visions and perspectives of media, science, statistics, and sensing over heterogeneous data sources and text mining algorithms, as well as some discussion regarding the implementation of data-driven methods through real-world examples. At the higher level, the methodology and concepts presented in the manuscript align well with the initiative and trend for building smart cities and urban digital twins. The topic is interesting and covers popular research areas in urban informatics. However, this manuscript covers a very wide spectrum of areas (e.g., global water observatory and COVID-19). I recommend the authors refine their scopes and focus. Even within the areas of global water observatory, there are too many perspectives (e.g., hydroinformatics, collaborative watershed management, urban water systems, public engagement, citizen science, and voluntary geographic information). There are also many different types of water resource management (e.g., surface water, groundwater, watershed planning, urban water supply and distribution system, flood and water hazards resilience/vulnerability, river management, and ecohydrology). The "Global Water Observatory" topic is too generic and broad and needs further refinement.

The authors could make this manuscript a review paper or an opinion paper that focuses on an urban data-driven digital twin approach to support urban management and use global water observatories and public health as case studies.

Detailed Comments:

Comment 1:

I think the manuscript only partially cited a portion of current literature. As an example, there are many public data sources for water resources data. I came from an urban computational science and hydroinformatics background in the U.S., where the government has open water data initiatives. Many real-time and historical government sensor data, such as the USGS streamflow, USEPA STORET water quality data, and FEMA Hazus flood data, are open to the public. University consortiums, such as CUAHSI and UCAR, provide online data-sharing and model-sharing platforms (e.g., CUAHSI Hydroshare) to share water resources data and simulations produced in academic research. The authors could include a more comprehensive review of the open data sources for both water resources and COVID data. Is there any government open water data initiatives or University consortiums data initiatives within the EU?

Comment 2:

I would suggest the authors provide a quantitative measure of the trend of different technologies and research areas using Elsevier Scopus or Google Scholar. These research platforms could provide you with statistics on the literature of a specific research area or contain specific keywords over a few years. A quantified bibliometric analysis is recommended.

Comment 3:

The visualization perspective of the topic is very weak in the current manuscript. There are many review articles that talk about visual computing approaches (information visualization, scientific visualization, and visual analytics) for COVID analysis and water resource management. Please see the example below:

- Leung, C. K., Chen, Y., Hoi, C. S., Shang, S., Wen, Y., & Cuzzocrea, A. (2020, September). Big data visualization and visual analytics of COVID-19 data. In *2020 24th International Conference Information Visualisation (IV)* (pp. 415-420). IEEE.¹

- Xu, H., Berres, A., Liu, Y., Allen-Dumas, M. R., & Sanyal, J. (2022). An overview of visualization and visual analytics applications in water resources management. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 105396.²

Comment 4:

In Figure 1, the authors mentioned the concept of digital twins. However, an important perspective on digital twins' features is missing from the discussion in the current manuscript. It is the "predictive analytics" capability, which differs from an urban digital twin from previous urban or hydrologic information systems (or decision support systems).

Comment 5:

Section V should provide more examples of digital twins in the water resources management sectors. More cases and real-world implementations should be discussed here. Below is an example; more examples/instances should be reviewed and discussed here.

- Alperen, C. I., Artigue, G., Kurtulus, B., Pistre, S., & Johannes, A. (2021, November). A hydrological digital twin by Artificial Neural Networks for flood simulation in Gardon de Sainte-Croix basin, France. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 906, No. 1, p. 012112). IOP Publishing³.

Comment 6:

The conclusion should also include some technical challenges and aspects of developing urban digital twins for the EU. As an example, what are potential big data or computing challenges from the cyber-infrastructure or HPC, respectively? Are there any data privacy or data residency concerns across EU countries?

I would recommend a minor revision for this manuscript. Overall the manuscript is in good shape and is well organized.

References

1. Leung CK, Chen Y, Hoi CSH, Shang S, et al.: Big Data Visualization and Visual Analytics of COVID-19 Data. *2020 24th International Conference Information Visualisation (IV), Melbourne, Australia*. 2020. 415-420 [Publisher Full Text](#)
2. Xu H, Berres A, Liu Y, Allen-Dumas M, et al.: An overview of visualization and visual analytics applications in water resources management. *Environmental Modelling & Software*. 2022; **153**. [Publisher Full Text](#)
3. Alperen C, Artigue G, Kurtulus B, Pistre S, et al.: A Hydrological Digital Twin by Artificial Neural Networks for Flood Simulation in Gardon de Sainte-Croix Basin, France. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*. 2021; **906** (1). [Publisher Full Text](#)

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Urban Digital Twins, Visual Analytics, Information Visualization, Hydroinformatics, Urban Science, Cyber Physical Systems, Watershed Management (with focus on soil erosion and in-stream sediment transport), Intelligent Transportation System, 3D City Modeling

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 28 Nov 2023

Joao Costa

We thank the thorough and useful review. We have added the suggested and other citations, and when possible we have exchanged web articles by research papers. Moreover, in the new submitted version of this paper, we have provided some more content regarding open data and visualisations. We have also improved the readability of the paper.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.